

BIOTECHNOLOGY'S EFFECT ON FOOD PROCESSING

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Introduction

Biotechnology is a branch of science concerned with the use of different living organisms in the development of usable things. In recent years, the application has been used in the fields of flavor improvement, food additives, and the creation of a broad variety of value-added products. Biotechnology is mostly used to create genetically engineered crops and genetically modified starter cultures. Biotechnology has ushered in significant advances in the world of food manufacturing, allowing for the development of items with increased shelf life and nutritional value. Another significant part of biotechnology's use in food manufacturing is flavor enhancement and vaccine development. The turning of raw materials into food or food into other types is referred to as food processing. Clean, harvested crops or butchered animal products are traditionally used in food processing to create appealing, marketable, and sometimes long-lasting food products. Processing helps to ensure food quality by reducing food waste and losses and increasing food supply and marketability. Food is also refined to increase the consistency and safety of the product (Balarabe *et al.*, 2017).

Fig. 1: Food Biotechnology: A Step Towards Improving Nutritional Quality of Food

Applications in food processing

Enzyme production: Microorganisms are mostly used in the agricultural manufacture of enzymes. The microorganisms are cultured in massive vessels, and the necessary enzymes are secreted into the atmosphere in which the microorganism fermented. Microbial action results in the secretion of enzymes in the form of metabolites. The enzymes formed by the above-mentioned process are then extracted, purified, and used in the food processing industry and for a variety of other purposes.

Table : Marketed Enzymes Produced Using Gene Technology (Olempska *et al.*, 2006)

Principle enzyme activity	Applications
Alpha- acetolated decarboxylase	Brewing
Alpha- amylase	Baking, brewing, distilling, starch
Catalase	Mayonnaise
Chymosin	Cheese
Beta-glucanase	Brewing
Alpha-glucanotransferase	Starch
Glucose isomerase	Starch
Glucose oxidase	Baking, egg, mayonnaise
Hemicellulase	Baking
Lipase	Fats, oils
Maltogenic amylase	Baking, starch
Microbial rennet	Dairy
Phytase	Starch
Protease	Baking, dairy, distilling, fish, meat, starch, vegetable
Pullulanase	Brewing, starch
Xylanase	Baking, starch

Enhancing taste: Scientists have been able to grow fruits and vegetables with longer shelf lives and improved flavor thanks to biotechnology. The following are examples of genetically engineered crops with improved flavor. Watermelon with no seeds, cherries, cabbage, eggplant, and pepper, to name a few. The removal of seeds from the aforementioned food crops increased the soluble sugar content, which improved the sweetness (Falk *et al.*, 2002). Biotechnology is used to modify fermentation processes in order to improve the scent of crops (Lawrence *et al.*, 1988). The volatile organic chemicals found in crops, such as tastes and aromas, are major determinants of customer adoption and market demand for many consumer products. There is a rivalry between flavors derived from agricultural sources and flavors derived from microorganisms. More than 100 industrial aroma chemicals and flavors are extracted from the use of conservative bio-engineering technology thanks to the application of biotechnology. The flavors can also be chosen using the over-producer range (Berger *et al.*, 2009).

Genetically Modified (GM) Foods: Foods that have been genetically engineered (GM) are those that have had their genetic material (DNA) altered, such as by inserting a gene from another body (Balarabe *et al.*, 2017). The introduction of GM foods can meet the need of proper surplus food supply in a quite a number of ways as follows: pest resistance, herbicide tolerance, cold tolerance, drought/ salinity tolerance, nutrition, pharmaceuticals etc.

Some genetically modified foods- Soybean, Maize, Rice, Tomato, Cotton, Potato etc.

Benefit and risk of biotechnology in food processing (Balarabe *et al.*, 2017).

Benefit-

- Increase food production.
- Less use of chemicals, pesticides, when GM crops grown.
- Less cost of production.
- More nutritious crops produced.
- Increase shelf life of crops etc.

Risk-

- GM crops are relatively costly.
- Fear of health risk etc.

Future of food biotechnology: Scientists can discover a quicker way to detect unwanted viruses and bacteria in food as research and development in the field of food biotechnology continues. This will help to reduce the risk of foodborne disease and keep food healthier to consume. Crops that can thrive in harsh environmental environments, such as excessive heat or drought, are now being grown using biotechnology. This could result in crops being planted on land that was previously unsuitable for cultivation. Scientists have since started to target specific allergy-causing proteins in foods, in the hopes of one day allowing people with food allergies to easily eat previously allergenic foods. Food biotechnology can also result in more nutritious foods for humans and animals. Foods with improved nutritional qualities are making their way to store shelves. Food biotechnology can help to fight chronic diseases by providing more healthful compounds, such as higher antioxidant and vitamin levels and lower levels of unhealthy fats (Council for Agricultural Science & Technology <http://www.cast-science.org>).

Conclusion

In today's world, the advantages of biotechnology outweigh the disadvantages. As it is critical to increase food production to satisfy the needs of an ever-increasing population. Although the safety of genetically modified (GM) crops is first checked by the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), the Food and Drug Administration (FDA), and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) before any GM crop is allowed to be grown and sold. Via training and exchange programmes for researchers, university and research institutes'

technological capacities in the fields of biotechnology, food manufacturing, bioprocess engineering, and food safety should be improved. Finding and consistency in the field of biotechnology should be promoted.

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